

Technical Report – end May 2023

**WP4 Demonstrators – D2. Sensitive Environments, Integrated Research
Infrastructure for Social Science (IRISS)**

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Purpose

The purpose of this document is to provide an update on the Sensitive Demonstrator (Work Package 4, Part 2) for the Integrated Research Infrastructure for Social Science (IRISS) project as funded by the Australian Research Data Commons (ARDC). Given the current state of the project and decision to extend the project to 30 June 2024, this report will only provide an update on current work and an overview of work intended to be done in the transition phase of the project.

1 Update on progress for Work Package D2

1.1 Brief overview of the sensitive demonstrator

Work package 4 demonstrator 2 aims to conduct a small-scale demonstration project to migrate and assess the outputs of IRISS services to assess their suitability for use in sensitive data environments. More specifically, this sensitive demonstrator aims to support three IRISS services: (1) a spatial data analysis demonstrator that will establish a new data product that leverages Census data outputs and the Geosocial service in IRISS; (2) a sensitive data analysis demonstrator that will assess the outputs of IRISS services to assess their suitability for use in sensitive data environments; and (3) the Australian Census Digital Collection demonstrator that will establish a new pilot collection that will create machine readable data assets and documentation from the Australian Census data collection. This is in line with the sensitive demonstrator’s core aim for Phase 1, which is “to assess the outputs of IRISS services such as new surveys and curation tools generated by the IRISS project for use in sensitive data environments.”

1.2 Progress update

Previous work on this demonstrator has focussed on the establishment of User Requirements in June 2022, technical outline of the Solution for WP4D2 in December 2022, and the establishment of a *project* workspace of the IRISS Service Pilot project within the Melbourne Institute Data Lab (MIDL) earlier this year. Due to delays with data access and extension of the project to 30 June 2024, the sensitive demonstrator’s plans to test IRISS services in sensitive environments will move to this transition phase (i.e., between phases 1 and 2 of the IRISS project). Phase 2 of the IRISS project is

intended to start 1 July 2024 and end 30 June 2027 but currently pending confirmation from the ARDC.

1.3 Technical details

The most current technical detail for the sensitive demonstrator is extensively covered in the “Work Package 4 – Service Pilot” report to the IRISS team (April 2023).

2 Sensitive demonstrator activities moving forward

IRISS Phase 2 has key planned areas of activity which are ‘embedding, expanding, extending and engaging’. The sensitive demonstrator (note: a name change to activities might occur in phase 2) is aligned with these key areas of activity. Three areas of work are planned for the sensitive demonstrator for IRISS Phase 2. These are:

1. Transition of IRISS services to a sensitive data environment
2. Activities to set up a cross platform approach to data sharing
3. Activities to support deeper data integrity checks within sensitive data pipelines

2.1 Transition of IRISS services to a sensitive data environment

Our demonstrator is a critical tool to ensure that IRISS services are being co-designed, built, and tested to ensure that they can be appropriately **extended** to a sensitive environment while maintaining usability. This was a focus area under phase 1 and will continue to be a focus area for the sensitive demonstrator in the transition phase and phase 2. These activities will leverage the dedicated project workspace inside the MIDL. See the “Work Package 4 – Service Pilot” report for more information.

It is expected that moving forward, our first focus would be migrate the following IRISS services to function within a sensitive data environment:

- GeoSocial data integration service
- DRAT: The Data Risk Assessment Tool
- VASSAL: Vocabulary and metadata services

Earlier in May we began discussions to understand the design of the GeoSocial integration service with the UQ and AURIN teams and their requirements for its appropriate function. These continued discussions will play a crucial role to ensure that these services function as required while being housed with a restricted environment. Co-design discussions around migrating other IRISS services has not commenced.

2.2 Cross platform approaches to sensitive data access

With work undertaken to demonstrate how sensitive data environments can be used for data integration activities, there remains a big gap in how sensitive data environments can work alongside each other in practice. Future work activity should explore data sharing models between secure research environments. This includes a standardisation model for sharing a settings’ security accreditation and certification credentials with ease. We believe this is also likely to be a key policy area given the continued growth of the cyber security threat landscape in Australia and across the world.

The MIDL is currently being assessed by the Office of the National Data Commissioner (ONDC) to be accredited as a data service provider under the upcoming DAT Scheme that regulates data sharing with data custodians in Australian Government. If successful, this scheme would place the MIDL in a key position to enable testing of IRISS services using a range of sensitive data assets (subject to

vetting and approval by relevant Data Custodians). This would help the IRISS **expand** their services to a larger group of data that are only accessible through dedicated secure data access environments like the MIDL. The Melbourne Institute also has a current engagement with the Australian Bureau of Services (ABS) to explore the hosting of a range of ABS data within the MIDL environment. The Melbourne Institute team is also building the Breaking Down Barriers Shared Data Environment, that is funded by the Paul Ramsay Foundation, to bring in a range of data to enable research to understand poverty and inform better service delivery in Australia. It is our hope that these engagements led by the Melbourne Institute can help the IRISS suite of services better **engage** with a range of data custodians in Australian Government, industry, and the not-for-profit sector.

2.3 Deeper data integrity checks within sensitive data pipelines

The work undertaken by the IRISS project team in Phase 1 around data collection using surveys (SPIRE) and data curation (CARDSS) showcase the need for an appropriate end-to-end series of services that enable better research practice within the social sciences. When we add in sensitive data and the access of these data within a sensitive data environment, there is a critical need to ensure appropriate transfer of knowledge around data collection and understand the data quality of input data (to the secure environment and subsequent research activities within the environment) to support data curation.

As part of Transition activities and Phase 2 activities, the Melbourne Institute and the MIDL team is intending to build a library of tests that **expand** the breadth of data that can be used for social science research that comes with better understanding of a data asset. This library is intended to be executed as a black box system and would consist of tests that are derived from best social science practices (such as type checks, distributional checks, consistency checks to name a few) and practices used outside of the social sciences such as in engineering and the computer sciences (such as unit testing and A/B testing).

At the Transition phase, work would be carried out to create a proof-of-concept test kit that works on a few measures using a popular social science quantitative data asset and provide example code for researchers to reproduce. At the end of Phase 2, work is to progress to build a library that researchers can include on projects and data pipelines within secure environments to ensure good input data quality.

3 Closing remarks

This brief report is only intended to provide an overarching plan for activities to be undertaken by the sensitive demonstrator team led by the Melbourne Institute. Additional details and plans for this demonstrator will be provided through future reporting into the transition period.